

Transforming businesses to reduce chronic non-communicable diseases through physical activity and mental health: A systematic literature review

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Chronic Non-Communicable Diseases (NCDs) are currently one of the greatest challenges facing health systems. The causes of these diseases, such as a sedentary lifestyle, alcohol consumption, smoking, and a history of high blood pressure in immediate family members, are major causes of death. They are, in general, preventable. Some forms of prevention are, for example, the reduction or elimination of tobacco and alcohol consumption, the consumption of healthy foods such as fruits and vegetables, and the reduction of the consumption of processed and ultra-processed foods, which are the most sold due to many factors, such as their flavor, the speed of their preparation and their durability after purchase. Some of the preventable causes of these diseases are physical inactivity, either due to the type of work or a sedentary lifestyle, excessive use of video games, prolonged use of screens, the use of motorized transport, and environmental pollution, which not only affects humans through pollution but also, to a lesser extent, through contamination in the kitchen of homes. Taking the above into account, it is essential to analyze the actions of public or private health companies that seek to reduce the appearance of NCDs, since medical treatments for these diseases are expensive and can leave disabling sequelae.

Keywords: Companies, Chronic diseases, Prevention, Sedentary lifestyle.

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1. INTRODUCTION

NCDs are a fundamental topic today and constitute an important object of research since they are part of the Sustainable Development Goals SDG and have become a challenge for all countries. According to the Pan American Health Organization PAHO and the World Health Organization WHO, NCDs are the main cause of death and disability in the world. These diseases cover a broad group of pathologies such as cardiovascular disorders, diabetes, strokes, cancer, and respiratory diseases [1]. Thus, they cause multiple health consequences and require long-term treatments; likewise, the WHO reports that, in 2005, the number of deaths caused by NCDs was 35 million people per year. However, in 2023, deaths from these diseases rose to 41 million people, which is equivalent to 71% of deaths that occur in the world. In the American continent, 5.5 million deaths are caused by some NCD each year.

Due to this urgent situation, governments of all countries have decided to create and adapt public health policies. These measures have resulted in the SDGs of September 25, 2015, which seek to ensure prosperity for all through specific goals set out in the 17 objectives that are intended to be achieved by 2030. For this reason, as indicated [2], at the annual WHO assembly it was suggested that health systems should be strengthened by implementing effective measures to better detect people at risk and provide pharmacological therapies and services to reduce deaths from heart attacks, strokes and diabetes. The prevention and treatment of mental disorders also require urgent action. WHO recognizes that political leadership needs to be improved to accelerate strategies to reduce the risk factors and causes of chronic non-communicable diseases.

In Colombia, through the Pan-American Cooperation, PAHO, and WHO, strategic planning actions were established to reduce the risk factors for NCDs, through the Ten-Year Public Health Plan of Colombia (PDSP, 2022-2031). This document stipulates social goals in matters of health and proposes achieving the Sustainable Development Goals. In addition, multisectoral strategies are established that cover areas such as education, the environment, economic development, and, of course, health.

Additionally, the country has worked on the Framework Agreement for Tobacco Control (FCTC), taxes on sugary foods, and foods high in saturated fats, among others, have been increased, and smoke-free spaces have been promoted. In addition, training activities have been implemented for professionals such as communicators and journalists, to expand media coverage and the quality of information on NCDs. More than 10,000 professionals in the country were trained on the PAHO/WHO Virtual Campus and more than 117 health administrators from 26 national territories were trained in the development of implementation plans for strategies to improve care for NCDs [3].

However, it is not known which companies are working specifically to achieve the goals proposed by the Sustainable Development Goals. In addition, in the literature on the subject consulted in this research, it is not clear which private companies in Colombia support or are part of the plans or organizations developed by the Government to carry out strategies to reduce NCDs and their consequences for health. Based on the above, the following research objectives have been proposed:

General objective:

- Identify healthcare companies focused on reducing NCDs through physical activity and mental health.

Specific objectives:

- To characterize health companies that operate in the promotion and prevention of NCDs through physical activity and mental health and to summarize articles on the subject.
- Identify the business models, intervention strategies, and population reach of the healthcare companies recognized in the study.

To achieve the stated objectives, this article presents a research methodology and the results obtained from scientific information and shows the current conditions of companies that strive to achieve the specific goal of reducing premature mortality from non-communicable diseases by one-third through prevention,

treatment, and the promotion of mental health and well-being, by 2030. This goal is consistent with the third objective of the SDGs, namely, *ensuring healthy lives and promoting well-being for all at all ages*. In light of the above, the question guiding this research is: How do health companies focused on physical activity and mental health contribute to the prevention and control of NCDs in the Colombian population?

2. METHOD

This article is the result of qualitative research, exploratory in scope. The design is non-experimental, cross-sectional and the sample is non-probabilistic [4].

- Sources: Information will be collected and analyzed from official sources, research reports, databases, and specialized publications such as Google Scholar, EBSCOHost, Business Source Ultimate, Scielo, and Redalyc.
- Techniques and instruments: qualitative data will be analyzed by triangulation of information.
- Procedure: First, for the bibliographic research process or literature review, a search using keywords in the databases was used. Second, the information was organized systematically in an Excel data table. Third, the information was analyzed by recognizing the main ideas, inferences, key concepts, etc. Finally, a diagram was made that presents the research findings.

3. RESULTS

To respond to the first objective raised, Table 1 is presented.

Table 1. Characterization of health companies in the P&P of NCDs

Name	Typology of company	Services and programs offered	Population object	Scope of action
Bodytech	Gym	Group training, Individual training, Nutrition and Fitness Programs. Physiotherapy.	13 to 70 years.	International
SmartFit	Gym	<i>Fitdance, Smartcross, Body Combat, SmartRumba.</i>	People with access to high-level physical activity practice	International
Colsanitas	Clinic	Prepaid medical companies offer plans with mental and physical health coverage.	The entire life cycles.	International.
EPS Sura	Clinic	Medical company prepaid with mental and physical health coverage.	The entire life cycles.	International.
Santa Fe Foundation	Health institution	Provides mental health services to people of all ages and conditions socioeconomic.	The entire life cycles.	National.
Ministry of Health and Social Protection	Governmental	National Strategy for the Prevention and Control of NCDs. Promotion of physical activity, nutrition health, and mental health.	The entire life cycles.	National.
Ministry of Sport	Governmental	Physical Activity for Health Program. Seeks to promote the regular practice of physical activity.	The entire life cycles.	National.
Ministry of Health and Social Protection	Governmental	Mental Health Program. Suicide prevention. Care for people with mental disorders. Promotion of mental health at work and school	The entire life cycles.	National.

Table 2 shows the results of the second research objective. According to the results, in the information search stage, twenty articles were found, of which four were of greatest interest.

The documents were read in detail and the most relevant information was selected. Information was obtained about how to achieve the reduction of NCDs, based on the collaboration of actors such as the Government, the Academy, and companies, among others.

The last work that appears in Table 2 was taken from a newspaper article, but it was striking because it specifically mentions companies and the programs they implement for young people in a city in Colombia.

Table 2. Literature review articles

Qualification	Author	Year	Summary	main idea	Concepts or keywords
Non-communicable chronic diseases: current magnitude and future trends [5]	Miguel Angel Serra Valdes, Melissa Serra Ruiz, Marleny Viera Garcia	2018	The treatment of chronic non-communicable diseases is currently one of the greatest challenges facing health systems worldwide. This is because these diseases affect all age groups and all regions and countries, regardless of their level of development. Cuba is not exempt from this. However, the World Health Organization points out that these diseases are inadequately managed, for different reasons, in most health systems. The objective of this article is to raise awareness of the current and future problems of chronic diseases, where prevention and health promotion continue to be the key weapon. Essential to combat the challenge.	The current problem of NCDs and the challenge of treating them in the coming years require us to draw up specific strategies in our sector. Continuing education regarding these diseases is necessary, especially in primary care with an updated approach. Better preventive work and, above all, promotional-educational work in the population are necessary.	Chronic disease; therapeutics; disease prevention; health promotion.
Physical activity for health and prevention of chronic non-communicable diseases (NCDs) [6]	Lourdes Cutti Riveros, Juan Jose Calleja Nunez, Emilio Manuel Arrayales Millan	2023	Regular physical activity generates social and health benefits, instills healthy lifestyles in the population, preventing sedentary lifestyles and non-communicable disease problems. The World Health Organization (WHO) considers physical activity as any bodily movement produced by skeletal muscles that requires energy expenditure, so an adequate level of physical activity complemented by a good diet reduces the risk of cardiovascular diseases, obesity, diabetes, breast and colon cancer, osteoporosis, and depression. This chapter seeks to analyze the population's access to the practice of physical activity for a healthy life in compliance with the Sustainable Development Goals. To do so, a review of the bibliography and secondary data is carried out that allows us to conclude that in the case of Mexico, 60.4% of the population over 18 years of age is physically inactive, and only 39.6% is considered physically active. Regarding the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), Mexico has made progress in the SDGs where great challenges remain. Part of the government's effort is to promote physical activity and sports as a physical culture strategy based on the Muévete Escolar modalities, Move Labor, Move Open Population Your Zone Move and Network National Communities in Movement.	It is important to contribute to the design of public policies aimed at promoting sport and physical activity, with viable strategies and actions to obtain results. Support the promotion of physical culture development through physical activity among the general population (children at the primary level, youth, adults, and older adults), in an inclusive manner. The inactive population can improve their health and well-being thanks to regular physical exercise, to reduce non-communicable diseases. Physical activity also brings with it social benefits that impact on the reduction of health care costs, the increase in production and participation in sports and recreational activities, the improvement of academic performance, and the reduction of absenteeism from work.	Sedentary lifestyle; Sustainable Development Goals; physical activity and healthy living.
Physical activity in the framework of primary health care, seen from the actors' perspective [7]	Laura E. Castro-Jimenez, Yenny P. Arguello-Gutiérrez and Diana A. Camargo-Rojas	2018	Identify the actions developed within the framework of physical activity from Primary Health Care (PHC), from the voice of the actors. Qualitative research, with an interpretive approach and narrative method, sought to identify, through in-depth interviews, the actions developed and the factors underlying the implementation of physical activity programs in the city of Bogotá. Regarding the actions developed, individualized and sectorial work is observed, without	The PHC, as a state strategy outlined in Law 1438 of 2011, under the principles of the Alma Ata Declaration of 1978 still in force, constitutes the path to achieve intersectoral work in favor of the health of populations, their human and social development, seeking control and	Motor activity; primary health care; public health; human resources.

			evidence of articulation between sectors and knowledge by the actors of all the programs present in the district. The professionals in charge of the implementation of the programs differ from those in charge of the organization and management of the same, since public and social management competencies are not recognized in professions such as physiotherapy, a degree in education and physical culture professionals, these positions being occupied mainly by engineers and social science professionals. The hiring of professionals continues to be a barrier to the continuity of the programs, as well as the lack of knowledge of the regulations and policies current.	management of the social determinants of health from different actors. This strategy requires political will, not only from the public sector but also from the private sector and academia. These actors, together with the community, will allow public policies to be implemented, to provide a real response to the needs perceived by the population.
AstraZeneca and the Plan Foundation seek to prevent non-communicable diseases.	Sofia Solorzano Cardenas	2021	This initiative was born after observing an increasing trend in early mortality related to NCDs since 2011 when the figure was 66%. For this reason, focusing on prevention and youth is essential to reduce the burden of non-communicable diseases. Now is the time to act to prevent this burden from increasing even further. This is a five-year program with which the organizations seek to contribute to improving the health and well-being of more than 100,000 people worldwide. 64,000 young people between 10 and 24 years old in three locations in Bogotá: Fontibón, Suba, and Engativá, through knowledge about this type of disease.	AstraZeneca and the Plan Foundation, a member of Plan International, will launch a youth health program in Colombia to prevent NCDs such as cancer, diabetes, cardiovascular and respiratory diseases.

In conclusion, it is hoped that this research will contribute to the understanding of the current panorama of health companies working in the promotion and prevention of NCDs in Colombia. The findings of the research can be used by health companies to improve their business models and intervention strategies, by authorities to develop more effective public policies, and by the academic community to generate new research on the subject.

However, based on the literature review, it is found that the information is not directly related to the role of companies in reducing non-communicable diseases. It is worth noting that an article in the newspaper El País specifically mentions one company, but, otherwise, the treatment of NCDs is carried out by the Colombian Government through Promotion and Prevention programs, in conjunction with a few Health Care Providers (EPS), but these do not indicate through publications in scientific journals how they address the issues of prevention and treatment of these diseases.

Likewise, thanks to the bibliographical research, it was found that many government documents inform, explain, and present programs to reduce NCDs; however, it was not found that the articles had any reach to the populations to whom their proposals are directed. To achieve these goals, everyone has to do their part: governments, the private sector, civil society, and people individually and collectively.

It is recommended that public or private companies publish the offers and scope of programs focused on reducing NCDs. In addition, this article can serve as a basis for continuing research on the topic of study, taking into account that there are public policies that support the programs designed and generally executed by the National Government and that, at the same time, invite companies to be part of the goals proposed by the SDGs. Thus, these policies motivate the creation of companies that contribute to change and the strengthening of healthy habits accessible to all. The reader is encouraged to lead a healthy lifestyle that includes a balanced diet, regular physical activity, and sufficient sleep. Physical activity and mental

health are two fundamental pillars for a healthy and full life; therefore, by investing in mental and physical health, it is possible to improve the quality of life and significantly reduce the risk of suffering from NCD-related pathologies.

REFERENCES

- [1] OPS/OMS Organización Panamericana de la Salud. (2023). Enfermedades no transmisibles. Recovered: <https://www.paho.org/es/temas/enfermedades-no-transmisibles>
- [2] El País (2018). Los 14 problemas de salud que más preocupan a la OMS. El País.
- [3] OPS/OMS Organización Panamericana de la Salud. (2023). La acción multisectorial, estrategia clave para el abordaje de las enfermedades no transmisibles en Colombia. Recovered: <https://www.paho.org/es/noticias/3-7-2023-accion-multisectorial-estrategia-clave-para-abordaje-enfermedades-no>
- [4] Hernández R. et al. (2014). Metodología de la Investigación. McGraw-Hill.
- [5] Serra M. et al. (2018). Las enfermedades crónicas no transmisibles: Magnitud actual y tendencias futuras. Revista Finlay 8(2), 140-148.
- [6] Cutti L. et al. (2022). La actividad física para la salud y la prevención para las enfermedades crónicas no transmisibles. Ediciones Comunicación Científica S.A. de C.V.
- [7] Castro L. et al. (2018). Actividad física en el marco de la atención primaria de salud, mirada desde los actores. Revista de Salud Pública 20(4), 415-421